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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LIPID PROFILE AND THYROID
FUNCTION TESTS IN PATIENTS OF PRIMARY
HYPOTHYROIDISM****¹Dr Muhammad Adnan Ahmad, ²Dr Maria Imtiaz, ³Dr Syed Fakhar Abbas Shah**¹Mohi-ud-Din Islamic Medical College, Mirpur, Azad Kashmir²Fatima Jinnah Medical College, Lahore³Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore**Abstract**

Objective: To know the Correlation with thyroid function tests and lipid profile in patients with primary hypothyroidism.

Study Design: A Cross Sectional Study.

Place and Duration: In the Endocrinology Department of Services Hospital Lahore for six months duration from September 2015 to March 2016.

Methods: 80 people (male and female) were included in the study. The patient group (G) (patients with primary hypothyroidism) was 40, and the remaining 40 were healthy subjects. Forty patients with primary hypothyroidism (TSH > 10 μ U) aged between 18 and 40 years were selected. The age of 40 years, euthyroid subjects and normal body mass index (BMI) were taken as control subjects. All subjects had a body mass index of 20 to 25 kg / m². All subjects had the same socioeconomic status, eating habits, lifestyle and physical activity were recorded. This was assessed by detailed interviews. Patients with diabetes mellitus and ischemia were excluded from the study. We also ruled out any pharmacological treatment that could alter lipid metabolism and thyroid function. No woman was postmenopausal. Patients whose BMI was higher than 25 kg / m² were not included in the study.

Results: A high positive association was observed between TC (total cholesterol) and TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism (r = 0.529). There was a significant positive correlation between TSH and LDLc (r = 0.4712) in patients with primary hypothyroidism. A strong positive association was also recorded between TAG and TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism (r = 0.5862) but there was no strong association between HDLc and TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism (r = 0.0480).

Conclusion: In conclusion, our results demonstrated the beneficial effects of L-thyroxine on lipid profile of patients with primary hypothyroidism. This study showed a decrease in total cholesterol, LDLc and TAG levels after treatment. The LDLc / HDLc ratio also decreased after treatment.

Key words: *thyroid, lipid profile, hypothyroidism.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Thyroid gland diseases are the most common endocrine disorders (Stephan et al 2006). The condition of the thyroid is an important indicator of the thyroid metabolism regulation. Thyroid diseases affect the metabolism of lipoproteins and are linked with variations in serum lipid levels leading to ischemic heart disease. Hypothyroidism is linked with high cardiovascular disease risk. Hypothyroidism is the generic term used to expose body tissues to abnormal thyroid hormones. Hypothyroidism is a risk factor because of its possible association with atherogenic lipid profile for atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease. Hypothyroid status may even cause early atherosclerosis. In humans, untreated hypothyroidism is a common cause of reversible hyperlipidemia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Cross Sectional Study was held in the Endocrinology Department of Services Hospital Lahore for six months duration from September 2015 to March 2016. 80 total patients (both male and female) were included in this analysis. The patient group (G) (patients with primary hypothyroidism) was 40, and the remaining 40 were healthy subjects. Forty patients with primary hypothyroidism (TSH > 10 μ Iu) aged between 18 and 40 years were included. The age of 40 years, euthyroid subjects and normal

body mass index (BMI) were included. Written consent was obtained from all subjects prior to the commencement of the study. All subjects were thoroughly examined. People who did not have the disease to interfere with lipid metabolism were included in the study. All subjects had a body mass index of 20 to 25 kg / m². All subjects had the same socioeconomic status, eating habits, lifestyle and physical activity. This was assessed by detailed interviews. Patients with diabetes mellitus and ischemia were excluded from the study. We also ruled out any pharmacological treatment that could alter lipid metabolism and thyroid function. There is no menopause in females. Patients whose body mass index was greater than 25 kg / m² were not included in the study.

Patients Group: In this group, 40 patients were treated with increasing doses of "thyroxine" (for the euthyroid condition, 50,100 and 150 g / day for each 20 days, the "treating physician dose can be adjusted"). Thyroxine 100-150 mg / day was administered as a maintenance dose for 30 days, until the patients become euthyroid proved from extracted blood sample. Control group: In this group, euthyroid and normal body mass index matched as control group were included. This group was strictly selected and evaluated previous exclusion and inclusion criteria.

Fig. 2: Correlation between TSH and LDLc In patients of primary hypothyroidism

RESULTS:

A high positive relation was observed between TC and TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism ($r = 0.535$). (Table 1 and Figure 1).

Table-1: Correlation In patients of primary hypothyroidism.

Correlation between	R-value	Significance
TSH and TC	0.535	S
TSH and LDLc	0.4712	S
TSH and TAG	0.5862	S
TSH and HDLc	0.0480	NS

A strong positive association was recorded between LDLc and TSH ($r = 0.4712$) in patients with primary hypothyroidism.

A significant positive association was observed between TAG and TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism ($r = 0.5862$). (Table 1 and Figure 3)

Fig. 3: Correlation between TSH and TAG In patients of primary hypothyroidism

There was no significant relation between HDLc and TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism ($r = 0.0480$). (Table 1 and Figure 4)

Fig- 4: Correlation between TSH and HDLc In patients of primary hypothyroidism

DISCUSSION:

Correlation of TS, LDLc, TAG and HDLc with TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism: A statistically significant positive correlation was found between TC and TSH, LDLc and TSH and GAD and TSH in patients with primary hypothyroidism. The findings of this study coincide with the results of Gomo and Ascott (1994) 6, a positive correlation between TC and TSH. In 1988, Althaus et al 7 observed a positive correlation between GAD and TSH. Caraccio et al. (2002) observed a positive correlation between LDLc and TSH.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, our results demonstrated the beneficial effects of L-thyroxine on lipid profile of patients with primary hypothyroidism. This study showed a decrease in TC, LDLc and TAG levels after treatment. The LDLc / HDLc ratio also decreased after treatment.

REFERENCES:

1. Beukhof, Carolien M., Elske T. Massolt, Theo J. Visser, Tim IM Korevaar, Marco Medici, Wouter W. de Herder, Jeanine E. Roeters van Lennep et al. "Effects of thyrotropin on peripheral thyroid hormone metabolism and serum lipids." *Thyroid* 28, no. 2 (2018): 168-174.
2. Feller M, Snel M, Moutzouri E, Bauer DC, de Montmollin M, Aujesky D, Ford I, Gussekloo J, Kearney PM, Mooijaart S, Quinn T. Association of thyroid hormone therapy with quality of life and thyroid-related symptoms in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA*. 2018 Oct 2;320(13):1349-59.
3. Guo, Ling-Chuan, Jianpeng Xiao, Yonghui Zhang, Shengbing Yu, Hualiang Lin, Guangning Su, Tao Liu et al. "Association between serum polybrominated diphenyl ethers, new flame retardants and thyroid hormone levels for school students near a petrochemical complex, South China." *Chemosphere*202 (2018): 476-482.
4. Zhang, Xiaohan, Wenbin Chen, Shanshan Shao, Guowang Xu, Yongfeng Song, Chao Xu, Ling Gao, Chunxiu Hu, and Jiajun Zhao. "A High-Fat Diet Rich in Saturated and Mono-Unsaturated Fatty Acids Induces Disturbance of Thyroid Lipid Profile and Hypothyroxinemia in Male Rats." *Molecular nutrition & food research* 62, no. 6 (2018): 1700599.
5. Ebrahimi, Neda, Fatemeh Taheri, Mitra Moodi, and Mahmoud Zardast. "The Effect of Educational Intervention on Body Mass Index and Thyroid Function Tests in Children and Adolescents with Obesity and Overweight." *International Journal of Pediatrics* 6, no. 8 (2018): 8101-8110.
6. Oh, Hye-Seon, Hyemi Kwon, Jonghwa Ahn, Eyun Song, Suyeon Park, Mijin Kim, Minkyu Han et al. "Association Between Thyroid Dysfunction and Lipid Profiles Differs According to Age and Sex: Results from the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey." *Thyroid* (2018).
7. Salihovic, Samira, Jordan Stubleski, Anna Kärman, Anders Larsson, Tove Fall, Lars Lind, and P. Monica Lind. "Changes in markers of liver function in relation to changes in

- perfluoroalkyl substances-A longitudinal study." *Environment international* 117 (2018): 196-203.
8. Golledge, Jonathan, Graeme J. Hankey, Osvaldo P. Almeida, Leon Flicker, Paul E. Norman, and Bu B. Yeap. "Plasma free thyroxine in the upper quartile is associated with an increased incidence of major cardiovascular events in older men that do not have thyroid dysfunction according to conventional criteria." *International journal of cardiology* 254 (2018): 316-321.
 9. Lebenthal Y, Levy S, Sofrin-Drucker E, Nagelberg N, Weintrob N, Shalitin S, de Vries L, Tenenbaum A, Phillip M, Lazar L. The natural history of Metabolic comorbidities in Turner syndrome from childhood to early adulthood: comparison between 45, X Monosomy and Other Karyotypes. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2018 Feb 9;9:27.
 10. von Roemeling, C.A., Caulfield, T.R., Marlow, L., Bok, I., Wen, J., Miller, J.L., Hughes, R., Hazlehurst, L., Pinkerton, A.B., Radisky, D.C. and Tun, H.W., 2018. Accelerated bottom-up drug design platform enables the discovery of novel stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1 inhibitors for cancer therapy. *Oncotarget*, 9(1), p.3.
 11. Lee, Jeongmin, Jeonghoon Ha, Kwanhoon Jo, Dong-Jun Lim, Jung-Min Lee, Sang-Ah Chang, Moo-Il Kang, Bong-Yun Cha, and Min-Hee Kim. "Male-specific association between subclinical hypothyroidism and the risk of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease estimated by hepatic steatosis index: Korea National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2013 to 2015." *Scientific reports* 8, no. 1 (2018): 15145.
 12. Glynn, N., Kenny, H., Salim, T., Halsall, D.J., Smith, D., Tun, T.K., McDermott, J.H., Tormey, W., Thompson, C.J., McAdam, B. and O'Gorman, D., 2018. ALTERATIONS IN THYROID HORMONE LEVELS FOLLOWING GROWTH HORMONE REPLACEMENT EXERT COMPLEX BIOLOGICAL EFFECTS. *Endocrine Practice*, 24(4), pp.342-350.
 13. Chalasani, Naga, Zobair Younossi, Joel E. Lavine, Michael Charlton, Kenneth Cusi, Mary Rinella, Stephen A. Harrison, Elizabeth M. Brunt, and Arun J. Sanyal. "The diagnosis and management of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease: practice guidance from the American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases." *Hepatology* 67, no. 1 (2018): 328-357.
 14. Begaye, Brittany, Paolo Piaggi, Marie S. Thearle, Kaitlyn Haskie, Mary Walter, Mathias Schlögl, Susan Bonfiglio, Jonathan Krakoff, and Karyne L. Vinales. "Norepinephrine and thyroxine are predictors of fat mass gain in humans with cold-induced brown adipose tissue activation." *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism* (2018).
 15. Pistollato, Francesca, Ruben Calderón Iglesias, Roberto Ruiz, Silvia Aparicio, Jorge Crespo, Luis Dzul Lopez, Piera Pia Manna, Francesca Giampieri, and Maurizio Battino. "Nutritional patterns associated with the maintenance of neurocognitive functions and the risk of dementia and Alzheimer's disease: A focus on human studies." *Pharmacological research* (2018).